

THE EVALUATION OF PUBLIC POLICY IMPLEMENTATION FAILURES AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

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Abstract

The study examines the root causes of Public Policy implementation failures. It further explores the mechanisms that will ensure successful policy implementation within the public sector. The main objective of the study is to establish and identify the factors that impede the successful implementation of government policies and to identify possible solutions to successfully formulate and implement public policies. The study adopted a conceptual approach relying heavily on secondary data. It is understandable, that the government's national and local spheres should want to downplay policy failure and trumpet apparent success, but to do so risks losing an understanding of why failure is so common and how it might be eradicated or at least minimised. The study examines the robust policy design mechanisms. The study seeks to identify significant policy risks and challenges. The study examines the root causes of Public Policy implementation failures. It further explores the mechanisms that will ensure successful policy implementation within the public sector. The main objective of the study is to establish and identify the factors that impede the successful implementation of government policies and to identify possible solutions to successfully formulate and implement public policies. The study adopted a conceptual approach relying heavily on secondary data. It is understandable that the government's national and local spheres should want to downplay policy failure and trumpet apparent success, but to do so risks losing an understanding of why failure is so common and how it might be eradicated or at least minimised. The study examines robust policy design mechanisms. The study seeks to identify significant policy risks and challenges. It is evident, that there is an increasing awareness that policies fail on their own merits; rather their progress is dependent upon the process of implementation. To better comprehend how to refine policy support it is first instructive to appreciate the nature of policy failure, logically the reasons why things go wrong should assist to guide the search for possible solutions. Successful policy implementation consists of four determinants, which are policy design, stakeholders, and their involvement, institution, and context as well as the implementation strategy. It is very important to consider these four aspects when executing public policy because this will alleviate policy implantation failures. The study concludes with the mechanisms and solutions of successful policy implementation.

Keywords: Policy, Public, government, implementation, failures, mechanisms, solutions.

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1. Introduction

It has been a trend that the likelihood of policy failure is at least as high as policy success. However, the currency of modern politics appears to be squarely that of failure indeed major failure. The way, in which offers of implementation support are couched and perceived, is significant in understanding their take-up and likely effectiveness. Acknowledging the frequency of policy failure, understanding the causes, and embracing the need to put in place policy support mechanisms, would seem to be well judged steps yet they go largely unaddressed [1].

It is evident, that there is an increasing awareness that policies fail on their own merits; rather their progress is dependent upon the process of implementation. The normatively attractive top-down view of policy and its implementation is predicated on three questionable assumptions: a chronological order, in which expressed intentions precede action; a linear causal logic whereby goals determine instruments and instruments determine results; and a hierarchy, within which policy formation is more important than policy implementation. The policy context is, however, now understood to be much more complex than had been previously recognised. The earlier literature on the "policy-implementation gap" has been supplemented in recent years by complex systems thinking, informed by notions of unpredictability, nonlinearity, and adaptability. Here the factors that shape and influence implementation are seen to be complex, multifaceted, and multileveled with public policies invariably [1].

[2] define public policies as the sets of activities governments undertake to address societal problems (problems that are recognized to affect collectives or to require a collective response). The scale and scope of these activities has expanded significantly in recent generations, as more problems have been deemed societal by social, economic, and political decision makers. New problems on public policy agendas differ from country to country but include social issues like education, health and welfare, environmental challenges like climate change, and concerns related to globalization like migration and inequality. Such new problems are represented in the four stories from public policy, which are health care costs, which became a major issue in France only in recent decades; education equity and quality emerged as a major agenda item in Brazil from the 1990s; unemployment received increased attention from South African policymakers after the 1994 elections; the need for emissions control was only embraced from the 1990s onwards in Australia.

[2] further asserts that millions of people are impacted negatively by the problems such policies are created to address, as is the authenticity of governments formulating and implementing the policies. It is thus significant to probe how often the policies succeed in containing or addressing their focal problems. Sadly, a prominent narrative suggests that public policies ‘often’ fail in so doing, and some even claim that this “failure is ubiquitous. “Policy failures seem prevalent, with no policy sector or country appearing immune to the operational challenges and political pitfalls of failure.

Inadequate means of navigating the factors of what constitutes policy failure is the important one. It is the obstacle to equate individual case studies, undertaking comparative research and indeed to comprehending the root causes of failure, which often gets mired in post-failure blame games. Unless we can find a mechanism of navigating the maze of what constitutes policy failure, we risk repeating the mistakes of the past, both in terms of producing policy failures and learning from failure [3]

The main aim of the research was to establish and identify the factors that impede the successful implementation of public policies and to identify possible solutions to successfully formulate and implement them. Apparently, there is no definitive theory of effective policy implementation from literature, and very few frameworks have been found acceptable as the basis of an analysis of the effectiveness of policy implementation. Therefore, the study seeks to evaluate the causes of public policy implementation failures and to identify the mechanisms, which are congruent with successful policy implementation. The research sought to identify the challenges of policy implementation, failures of policy implementation as well as the possible mechanisms and solutions that will address the failures of policy implementation.

2. Materials and Methods

The study used databases, such as Sabinet, Sage Publishers, ResearchGate, JSTOR and Scopus, to search for the literature. The study adopted the conceptual approach and heavily relied on secondary data. Secondary data, used in the study, was gathered from relevant books, journals, conference proceedings, published articles. The books consulted were those relating to failures of public policy implementation as well as possible solutions for successful public policy implementation. Several journals focusing on public policy implementation failures and the mechanisms of successful policy implementation were also used.

3. Results

3. 1. Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the Group Theory because its main objective is to identify the causes of public policy failures and possible solutions to ensure successful policy implementation. Group Theory has assigned too much power to organised interest groups and has left policymakers to respond to the demands coming from these interest groups. It also seems as if public officials are left on the side of the road. The interest groups play a significant role in the policy-making process.

3. 1. 1. Group Theory

[4] avers that “public policy is the product of the group struggle”. The group model emphasizes the influence of interest and pressure groups. A collection of individuals can be defined as

a group. As per the description of group theory, the fight among the different social groups of the society resulted in public policy. Group struggle produced the public policy. The resourcefulness of the interest groups is the chief agent for the policy change. Interest groups interact and pressurize the policymakers for self-interest and first choice. The political system plays its role in the establishment and enforcement of compromising situations among the different conflicting interest groups in society. These individuals have several common interests and base on their common interests; they interconnect with some frequency.

[5] accentuates that the central practice of the Group Theory is that interaction among groups is a critical ingredient in politics. Public policy is thus a temporary point of compromise, reached during competition between mosaics of numerous interest groups with cross-cutting membership. The ability of the group that is favoured at one point to sustain its gain depends on its power to counteract the powers of other groups that would make efforts to tilt decisions to their favour. It is this type of competition between groups that determine the pattern of allocation of societal resources. The locus of power in the society changes from time to time, depending upon the group that succeeds in exerting its own supremacy over the others. Accordingly, the power to determine a policy direction changes with the changes in the fortunes of each or a combination of these groups. It is in appreciating the fluidity of power base in society that Latham contends that what we regard as public policy is a temporary equilibrium, reached during the inter-group struggle. As soon as the equilibrium point is altered in the favour of new groups another policy will emerge or the old policy will be modified. Politics in essence entails a dynamic equilibrium, created by the struggle between different groups. The legislature acts only as a referee to the inter-group struggle, and it ratifies the victories of the successful coalitions, as well as record the terms of the surrender, compromises, and conquest in the form of statutes or Bills.

[6] avows that the group theory encompasses organised interest groups in the public policy-making process and the interaction among the groups is a “central fact of politics”. It defines these actors as continually fighting for their voices to be heard. Therefore, the group theory can be summarised as the clash of voices amongst organised interest groups. Members that can be categorised as belonging to the group theory can range from, for example, music recording companies to even members of the agricultural sector. The group theory is relevant and necessary in public policy because different groups play an important role and could influence public policy inputs. The group theory encompasses organised interest groups in the public policy-making process and the interaction among the groups is a “central fact of politics”. It defines these actors as continually fighting for their voices to be heard. However, the shortfall of the group theory is that it favours those groups that are more organised; have more numbers; have financial means; have political affiliations; are popular and have made connections with policymakers.

3. 2. Policy making cycle

[7] postulates that the policy cycle framework originates from the idea of organizing and ordering the convolution of policymaking. It is a heuristic tool, through which different stages of the ongoing and never-ending dynamics of policy processes can be segmented and then analysed. The use of the policy cycle image and related stages is a generic practice in public policy. Its principal function is to help order the analysis of the complex and apparently chaotic dynamics of policymaking. The simple, apparently rough idea is to divide the flux of policymaking into stages. It is analytically useful because, by dividing the policy process into different stages, it is possible to better grasp the specific dynamics occurring in any given stage. These stages can also be considered arenas where different actors play different roles, while pursuing their own goals. For example, if we consider a five-stage format (agenda setting, formulation, decision-making, implementation, and evaluation), for every stage, a final output can be expected: definition of the problem, definition of the possible alternatives, decision, the actual realization of the expected goal, and expenses of broader public.

Five stages of the policy making cycle

[8] outlines five stages of the Public Policy-making cycle, which are agenda setting, policy formulation, decision making, implementation and evaluation. The stages are discussed below as follows.

– Agenda Setting

The first stage entails identifying a problem that needs government intervention and proposing it as an issue to the public. Agenda setting represents a ‘laundry list of to-do items’ that the government is seriously prioritising and considering. At this stage, no decision will have been made about how that a problem might be addressed, and whether that solution will ever be implemented.

– Policy Formulation

At this stage now that the government has identified the problems it would like to resolve, it will require the appropriate mechanisms about to decide how it will address them. The policy crafting stage is the setting of objectives based on a problem defined and identified in agenda-setting, and consideration of alternative actions to achieve those objectives. There are various alternative perspectives on how this stage happens. These range from more general organisational decision theory to specific long term planning approaches for governments. Now that the public agenda has problems to choose from, and solutions have been proposed, the next step is for government is to commit to the articulation of the two in the decision-making stage.

– Decision Making

The decision-making process is not the isolated rational exploration of alternatives. Rather, it is a bargaining process by those with interests in the problem with the decision-making levels of government to advance those interests. In addition to the pursuit of and discourse between different interests, there can be constraints, over which problems and challenges can be selected, and which solutions can be proposed. These can include budget and capability constraints

– Implementation and Evaluation

Once decided on, the proposed actions to address the policy problem need to be implemented. Public policy implementation is what happens between the government’s intention to act, and the effect of that action. Policy implementation should entail clear solution details. For example, a clear interpretation of the solution and which organisations should be involved in implementing it. It should also consist of vivid allocation of resources to organisations participating in the solution and clear delegation of decision-making authority.

– Evaluation

The final step in the policy cycle is to analyse and measure success. Initially, we may consider rigorous, quantitative, scientific evaluation as the go-to approach here. However, the literature refers to a wider scope of evaluation activity to include values and assessments beyond the restrictions of traditional perspectives. Examples of these include opinions of the wider public, media and external audits of government agencies and departments.

3. 3. Public Policy Implementation

Implementation Support

[1] asserts that tracking performance delivery alone is unlikely to be sufficient to ensure effective implementation, especially where the policy is complex and long-term in nature. The question then arises as to whether some type of implementation support mechanism might be required and, if so, that initiative is relevant. All such initiatives would need close liaison with, and the comprehension of, the position of the implementing agencies. Three purposes have been identified: managing and regulating; problem-solving; and capacity building.

– Managing and regulating

Here the focus is on the identification of procedures for the measurement and scrutiny of performance and ensuring required standards are met. The detailed tracking of multiple implementation agencies is a formidable and costly task. The temptation will be to allow agencies to self-assess their performance, which in turn makes the risk that performance rating will be exposed to “grade inflation.” It is an approach better suited to implementation tracking than to implementation support.

– Problem-solving

The assumption here is that a problem has been clearly and adequately well-defined to permit a close focus on how to resolve it. This could be pursued in a various way, such as technical support, troubleshooting, the brokering of areas of conflict and persuading the usage of research

and evidence. It is likely to require a flexible staffing model able to respond to the different needs and demands of local contexts.

– Capacity building

Whereas problem-solving focuses on “what” questions, capacity building concentrates on the “how.” It involves investing in skills and competencies that will be sustainable in meeting future implementation challenges. Training, peer learning, information, guidance, project management skills and other such interventions could all have a part to play. This sort of initiative has informed the World Health Organisation’s Regional Office for Europe’s health systems transformation initiative, which is focused on how to make change happen and put in place the necessary infrastructure for this to materialise.

[9] posits that today we are living in the era, in which transformation becomes imminent. It is evident, that the world is forever keen on targeting and attaining quality education, comprehensive and rapid socio-economic development, establishing independent systems, and good governance, which is on the brink of its renaissance. The governance has been busy in a major attempt to put the nation on a path to improving socially, politically, and economically. In addition, the application of education policy is a purposeful and multidirectional change process, aimed at operationalising a particular public policy that can influence a multi-level education system. It is purposeful to the extent that the process is supposed to alter education according to specific policy objectives; it is multidirectional as it can be inflected by performers at various levels. It is multidirectional because it can be inflected by role players at different points in the education scheme; it is contextualized in that organizations and societal aspects and trends, i.e., in culture, demography, politics and economy, influence the education system and the way a phenomenon affects the education system.

3. 4. Challenges of Public Policy Implementation

[10] accentuates those challenges of policy implementation in Africa could link to poor planning, political instability, and bureaucratic bottleneck, the deliberate imposition of policy, complete alteration to the plan if it is not favourable to the implementers or civil servants, saddled with the responsibility to implement it. Africa has no problem with policy plan or formulation other than the challenge of policy implementation. One of the problems of policy implementation is the failure to get the target beneficiaries to participate in the policy process. Policies imposed by the government without considering whether it meets the needs of the people or not.

[10] further avers that the current trends in Africa are to adopt foreign made solutions to its plethora of problems and the implementation of such policy often undermines the capacity of local intellectual resources that resonates with local issues. These tend to deepen the underdevelopment of local talents and deprive them of the opportunity to master the problem on their terms. These also entails the failure of policymakers to take into consideration the social, political, economic, and administrative environment when analysing policy implementation and this often results in policy failure. It has become a recurrent decimal for the international community to impose a policy in the form of goal setting like Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and now Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). According to [11] the following core problems and challenges emerged concerning Public Policy Implementation (PPI) within the context of a new democracy within the South African perspective:

Firstly, lack of participation, comes due to a lack of consultation. The problem of a lack of consultation between government and relevant stakeholders is that it defies South Africa’s Constitution, as the Constitution clearly stipulates a participatory democracy. Therefore, the lack of consultation between government and relevant stakeholders is a direct “gun-wound” to South Africa’s young democracy. Second, the lack of consultation can lead to non-compliance, which can have a detrimental effect on South Africa’s young democracy. Third, applying Western solutions to African problems is a problem. Fourth, the fact that Public Policy Implementation (PPI) is time-consuming and challenging to implement is one of the problems of PPI in South Africa. Fifth, lack of knowledge, skills, experience, and expertise is a problem and a challenge. Last, the absence of a common theory on PPI is a major obstacle to successful PPI.

3. 5. Public Policy Implementation Failures

[3] avers that policy failures seem prevalent, with no policy sector or country appearing unsusceptible to the operational challenges and political pitfalls of failure. A simple internet search for news stories at the time of writing produced headings, such as ‘Obama’s Foreign-Policy Failures Go Far Beyond Iraq’, ‘Homelessness Crisis. Show “Social Policy Failure” and ‘Prisons Face Overcrowding Due to Policy Failure’. We can also add to this list, other prominent attributions of policy failure, such as the Poll Tax and Child Support Agency (UK), home insulation program (Australia), response to the global financial crisis (Iceland), ‘No Child Left Behind’ (USA) and Guantanamo Bay detention camp (USA). Disputes over whether a policy has ‘failed’ are commonplace. Allegations of policy failure from opposition parties, the media, and others, typically produce counter discourses from supporters attempting to shore up support for policies by claiming that the alleged failure is in fact a success.

[12] asserts that policy failures are often perceived to be not deliberate and anomalous events, about which well-intentioned governments can learn why they occurred and how they can be rectified. These assumptions colour many of the results from modern studies of policy learning, which remain positive that ongoing policy problems can be addressed through technical learning and lesson drawing from comparative case studies. Practical policy failures, like successes, are also common sources of studies of policy learning and lesson-drawing. While attention has been paid in the literature to such failures, however, it has not been uniform and, as with policy success, requires more subtle distinction in their study and in the types of lessons, which can be drawn from failures, than is typically the case. Program failures are only one kind of policy failure, which may also fail on the political front or simply fail to address a problem. An exclusive focus on program elements or components further reinforces the tendency in the literature to highlight technical issue and “shallow” learning. Further, like success, failures also differ significantly in extent and immensity. They can be large or small, long-term, or short-term, for example, and some may be highly visible, while others may be discernible only to experts [12].

[1] posits that to better understand how to improve policy support it is first instructive to appreciate the nature of policy failure – logically the reasons why things go wrong should help to guide the search for potential solutions. There is now growing interest in the notion of “policy failure”, “failure” resides at the extreme end of a success–failure spectrum where it is characterized by absolute nonachievement. Such a situation will be unusual. It is evident, that “failure is rarely unequivocal and absolute even policies that have become known as classic policy failures also produced small and modest successes.

[1] further identifies four broad contributors to policy failure, which are overly optimistic expectations; implementation in dispersed governance; inadequate collaborative policymaking; and the vagaries of the political cycle. The contributors to policy failure are discussed below as follows:

– The persistence of policy failure

To better understand how to improve policy support, first, it is instructive to appreciate the nature of policy failure logically and the reasons things go wrong should help to guide the search for potential solutions.

– Overly optimistic expectations

It might be especially thought that the bigger and more expensive policies “major projects” would be those, most carefully assessed for risk, yet “over-optimism” was the title, given to an influential review of failure in major government projects.

– Implementation in dispersed governance

Policies, formulated at the national level, may face the challenge of ensuring some degree of consistency in delivery at the subnational level, a process that is especially fraught where the subnational level has some separate degree of political authority.

– Inadequate collaborative policymaking

Policymaking has tended to be developed in distinct administrative siloes, even though most interventions will almost certainly have wider implications that affect external parties. Moreover, despite growing academic interest in developing ideas and tools for promoting inter-organisational partnering; the improvement has been at best patchy and limited.

– Vagaries of the political cycle

Politicians tend not to be held accountable for the outcomes of their policy initiatives in the event of failure. The likelihood is that they will have moved on or moved out. One consequence of this is that they are too easily attracted to the prospect of short-term results. This can lead to the pushing through of policies as quickly as possible, rather than getting involved in the messy, protracted, and frustrating details of how things might work out in practice. In general, there is evidence to suggest that the political will necessary to drive long-term policymaking tends to dissipate over time.

3. 6. Mechanisms and Possible Solutions for Successful Policy Implementation

[13] opines that the process of implementing and evaluating public policies is best understood by considering the process of making public policies as an operation that has several sub-processes articulated. A policy is the articulation of aims and specified activities that can help end a particular problem once implemented. Public Policy is about things and actions that the government has deemed right and wrong for people. In case the government decides to do a particular thing that is of community interest without success in the achievement of the desired outputs, policy analysts make a concerted effort to divulge the rationale behind the failure of public policy. One approach for doing this is to peruse distinct shortcomings at the implementation phase and the policy formulation phase. In case inadequacies are identified in each phase, it means that the policymaking process invalidated some significant aspects that would ascertain that every step, taken in the crafting and implementation phases, is congruent with the desired final goal and objective of the public policy. Dereliction to include it in both phases makes it difficult for the people formulating and implementing the policy to detect certain inadequacies. Such shortcomings may truncate into the failure of the policy to deliver the anticipated outcomes upon full implementation.

Once policies are formulated, the next phase involves their implementation. Public policy implementation refers to the exercising of a particular public policy decision as directed by the law, court, or any administrator's prescriptions. It takes two paradigms, bottom-up and top-down. The bottom-up approach is initiated by singling out the chain of people who take part in offering any service to each or all local areas by interviewing them on their ambitions, schemes, actions, and contacts. The bottom-up approach holds that the public policy implementation process is inseparable from the formulation phase. The roles of administrators and politicians are also deemed as critical in the success of the formulation and implementation of the policies from the paradigms of the bottom-up approach [13].

[9] outlines four factors for successful policy implementation, which are policy design, stakeholders and their involvement institution and the context of the implementation strategy. The factors are discussed in detail as follows:

– Design of the policy

The policy design is the way, in which a policy is discussed and framed the logic it indicates between the policy issue and the solution it provides, and the feasibility of the latter largely determines whether and how a policy can be promulgated.

– Policy Justifications

A policy can react to a need or perception of a need that has to be obviously outlined to promote the solution's formulation, legitimacy, and execution.

– Policy logic

The clarity of policy objectives and their priorities in policy laws influence the implementation agencies' operational level. Furthermore, different actors may have distinct interpretations of policy objectives.

– Feasibility

Decision makers face several shortcomings when crafting a strategy, including the need to pass the bill, which may encourage them to focus more on what they can do politically than practically.

– The Stakeholders and their Engagements

Individuals and organisations implement strategies that make them central to the implementation process both because of their own features and because of their relationships with other determinants. Political actors, such as instructional experts or engineers: educators, administra-

tors, scientists, and scholars; economists and financial experts: costs and funding ability, effectiveness, and productivity of investment in education, economic and employment related instructional objectives; researchers: like research, better integration should be achieved. Administrators: like procedures, tasks, and organisation of administrative structures; planners: a systemic vision of the education industry as a whole; senior public officials, ministers of education/major educational organizations, other educational organizations, government agencies and intergovernmental bodies and official actors, stakeholders, and politics.

– The Institutional and Societal Context

The institutional setting entails the formal and informal social constraints that govern the implementation process in each government system. The other policies in place in government and other sectors also need to be considered because they may facilitate or hinder the implementation process.

– The Implementation Strategy

The implementation strategy refers to the operational plan that directs the process to make the policy happen in effect. A clear separation of policy formation from policy implementation with in line model lists six criteria factors for effective policy implementation, which are policy objectives, which are clear and consistent, the program based on a valid causal theory, the implementation process, which is structured adequately; implementing officials are committed to the program's goals; interest groups and (executive and legislative) sovereigns are supportive; there are no detrimental changes in the socioeconomic framework conditions.[14] also outlines five criteria for successfully implementation of policy as follows:

– Innovations, designed to improve student achievement, must be technically sound.

– Successful innovation requires change in the structure of a traditional school.

– Innovation must be manageable and feasible for average teacher.

– Implementation of successful change efforts must be organic rather than bureaucratic; and

– Avoid the “do something, anything” syndrome. A definite curriculum plan is needed to focus efforts, time, and money on sound, rational content, and activities.

Regimes are continually looking for new and better ways to achieve their policy objectives. While policy implementation has been acknowledged as critical in closing the gap between policy promises and policy outcomes, the process itself is complex and multi-faceted and has yet to be well-comprehended. Policy implementation is generally defined as a series of activities, undertaken by government and others to achieve the goals and objectives articulated. While governments and public administrators have clearly been interested in, and committed investments toward, implementation supports as part of the usual policy-making processes, most scholarly works have concentrated on formulating policy to be ‘implementable or describing the factors that are significant in the implementation process [15].

The limitations of the study are that the root causes of policy implementation failures are not adequately researched and because of that the current literature review is insufficient. The conceptual approach, adopted by the study, limited the researcher from interaction with policy makers, policy practitioners and the beneficiaries of designed policies.

The author interprets the results adequately to substantiate the discourse around the failures of public policy implementation and the possible solution to address the increasing failures in various governments globally. The key success factors in public policy implementation, which are evaluated within the context of specific problems, and critical factors, which are affecting implementation, differ, and “success-prone” policies are not always obvious. Successful implementation is deemed to be partially predetermined by good leadership that can be important to a political hidden hand that guides organized and desperate interest to converge in support of implementing policy. Operative and successful policy implementation is the blood life of national development. The successful implementation strategy refers to the operational plan that guides the process to make the policy happen in effect.

Study Limitations. The study adopted a conceptual approach that limited the author to interact with relevant stakeholders responsible for public policy implementation. Different authors had differing opinions regarding public policy failures and successful implementation, which makes it difficult for the author to authenticate their different views. If the study was empirical

the author could have gathered the findings and interpreted them according to the participants' responses.

Prospects for further research. Administrative, inadequate resources, and policy ambiguity, are the prospects that must be further researched because most new and young democracies face policy implementation challenges. The challenges are linked to a scarcity of capacity, which is attributed to inadequate resources ranging from technical, skills, and resources. Another prospect for further research is policy implementation support because it ensures a common ground, developed with key stakeholders at the initiation stage, which is also applied to those putting policies into effect in managerial and professional roles.

3. 7. Recommendations

The study revealed public policy challenges and failures of successful policy implementation. Therefore, it is of vital importance for the study to outline the recommendations that will offset these public policy challenges, failures, and gaps. The study outlines the following recommends:

- For policy to be successfully implemented policy practitioners must ensure that policy design preparation is prioritised.

- It is further recommended, that policy design preparation must include exploration of policy options and their feasibility with key implementation agencies, creation of forums for collaborative policy design.

- The more consensual the design process the less the likelihood of disagreements at the implementation stages, development of policy design assurance frameworks, which include identification of significant implementation risks and challenges along with risk management strategies

- It is recommended, that efficient and effective policy implementation would require inputs of sound managerial and administrative capabilities to avoid the policy implementation gap and failure.

- Production of robust implementation statements, which resonates with clear expectations of what should reasonably be expected to be delivered and under what circumstances, use of the best available evidence bases to inform policy design

- Agreement on what would constitute an adequate funding stream for anchoring the policy and achieving the program objectives and to ensure the agencies, tasked with implementation, can reasonably be expected to succeed in the task.

- The study further recommends policy tracking as the essential element of successful policy implementation. Policy tracking includes aspects, such as two-way communication processes, which are progress reports from implementation agencies to the policy-making centre; responses back from the centre to implementing agencies, use or creation of intermediary bodies between the policymaking and policy implementing levels.

- It is also recommended, that public policy practitioners must embrace policy implementation support, which includes ensuring the common ground, developed with key stakeholders at the preparation stage, which is also applied to those putting policies into effect in managerial and professional roles, which are the understanding of bottom-up discretion and dilemmas, recruitment, and development of a cadre of experienced and trusted “implementation brokers” to offer support, tailored to local contexts.

- Offer implementation support where it is needed or requested. Ongoing assistance with problem-solving and capacity-building to develop sustainable implementation skills and knowledge are essential to successful policy implementation. The study further recommends that policy practitioners must ensure the existences of the policy implementation review, which include, short, medium, and longer-term review landmarks as well as clarity on what should have been achieved by when, routine use of action research for formative and summative evaluations and political acknowledgment that complex policies need to be given time to demonstrate achievements, which are the costs and benefits that will be unevenly distributed over time.

- Lastly, the study recommends that policy makers and practitioners must design policies, which are implementable, and participation of beneficiaries must be encouraged by pressure groups and government.

4. Conclusion

The paper sought to investigate public policy implementation failures and to identify mechanisms and possible solutions to ensure successful public policy implementation. The study explored the theoretical approach that will contribute towards solutions of successful policy implementation. The theoretical approach was examined by reviewing and summarising existing literature on the topic. This has been done to identify solutions and facilitate the practical improvement of public policy implementation. Considering this literature review, several points have arisen. Firstly, stages of public policy making, challenges of public policy, policy implementation failures and mechanisms and possible solutions for successful policy implementation.

It is evident, that success in implementation, evaluated within the context of problems, and critical factors affecting implementation varies, and “success prone” policies are not always obvious. Effective implementation is said to be partially predetermined by good leadership that can be the significant political hidden hand that guides organized and desperate interest to converge in support of implementing policy. Effective and successful policy implementation is the key success factor to national development. Based on the exposition, given by the study, it is obvious, that policy implementation is the process of transforming designed policy into real life. It dispenses the operational area of function in operationalising the public policy declared by government. In the implementation of public policy, the combination of human, material, machine, and money is highly necessary.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest

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References

- [1] Hudson, B., Hunter, D., Peckham, S. (2019). Policy failure and the policy-implementation gap: can policy support programs help? *Policy Design and Practice*, 2 (1), 1–14. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2018.1540378>
- [2] Andrews, M. (2021). Successful Failure in Public Policy Work. Centre for International Development Studies at Harvard University. Available at: <https://bsc.cid.harvard.edu/files/bsc/files/2021-12-cid-wp-402-successful-failure.pdf>
- [3] McConnell, A. (2015). What is policy failure? A primer to help navigate the maze. *Public Policy and Administration*, 30 (3-4), 221–242. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0952076714565416>
- [4] Mustafa, G., Yaseen, Z., Arslan, M., Imran, M., Nisa, Z. U. (2021). Theoretical approaches to study the public policy: an analysis of the cyclic/stages heuristic model. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354681898> _ Last accessed: 11.06.2022
- [5] Anyebe, A. (2018). An Overview of Approaches to the Study of Public Policy. *International Journal of Political Science*, 4 (1), 8–17. doi: <https://doi.org/10.20431/2454-9452.0401002>
- [6] Selepe, M. M. (2021). An Overview of Mechanisms of the Development of Public Policy for Good Governance. *African Journal of Development Studies*, 11 (3), 203–225.
- [7] Capano, G., Pritoni, A. (2020). Policy Cycle. *The Palgrave Encyclopedia of Interest Groups, Lobbying and Public Affairs*, 1–7. doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-13895-0_69-1
- [8] Warner, C. (2022). Perspectives in Public Policy – The Policy Cycle. Available at: <https://www.online.auckland.ac.nz/2022/04/11/perspectives-in-public-policy-the-policy-cycle/> Last accessed: 21.06.2022
- [9] Tezera, D. (2019). Factors for the Successful Implementation of Policies. *Merit Research Journal of Education and Review*, 7 (8), 92–95. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3382780>
- [10] Ajulor, O. V. (2018). The challenges of policy implementation in africa and sustainable development goals. *PEOPLE: International Journal of Social Sciences*, 3 (3), 1497–1518. doi: <https://doi.org/10.20319/pijss.2018.33.14971518>

- [11] Tebele, M. M. (2016). Problems and challenges related to public policy implementation within the South African democratic dispensation: A theoretical exploration. North-West University.
- [12] Leong, C., Howlett, M. (2021). Policy Learning, Policy Failure, and the Mitigation of Policy Risks: Re-Thinking the Lessons of Policy Success and Failure. *Administration & Society*, 54 (7), 1379–1401. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/00953997211065344>
- [13] The Implementation of Public Policy Analytical Essay Examples (2019). IvyPanda. Available at: <https://ivypanda.com/essays/the-implementation-of-public-policy/>
- [14] Bullock, H. L., Lavis, J. N. (2019). Understanding the supports needed for policy implementation: a comparative analysis of the placement of intermediaries across three mental health systems. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 17 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-019-0479-1>
- [15] Ornstein, A., Hunkins, F. (2018). *Curriculum foundations, principles, and issues*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.

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